

The Level of Job Satisfaction Among Faculty Members at King Faisal University in Saudi Arabia from Their View point

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 13, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: October 14, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Job Satisfaction, Faculty Members, King Faisal University, Saudi Arabia.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13931536</p>	<p><i>The study aimed at identifying the level of job satisfaction among faculty members at King Faisal University in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and to reveal differences in the responses of faculty members about their level of job satisfaction according to study variables: gender, nationality, college, academic rank, and experience. The descriptive approach was adopted by building a questionnaire consisting of (36) items, divided into five areas: job, social relations at work, salaries and incentive, direct administration, professional development, and promotions. The study tool was applied to (252) faculty members from various scientific and humanitarian colleges. The findings showed that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members at King Faisal University was high. The field of social relations at work came at a very high level, while the field of salaries and incentives came at a moderate level. It was also found that there were no statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) attributed to the variables: college, academic rank, nationality, and the number of years of experience. While the differences were due to the gender variable and in favor of males.</i></p>

Introduction

Effective administration of university education plays an essential part in achieving the desired university goals and also plays a key role in raising the productivity of faculty members who are the mainstays of university education, which allows university institutions to practice democratic administrative patterns based on involvement in planning and decision-making (Morsi, 2002).

Terpstra & Honoree (2006) see that many educational institutions are clearly interested in the levels of job satisfaction for their employees, including administrators and faculty members, as job satisfaction is one of the significant institutional variables due to its association with the levels of performance and motivation of employees

The importance of studying job satisfaction among faculty members in public education institutions arose due to the increased concern of attaining job satisfaction during the exercise of their duties. The role of faculty members in shaping the future of their societies, and the power they possess in developing and transferring goals and objectives to public education institutions also helped in giving more attention to this area (Tanash, 1990).

Interest in job satisfaction also emerged because of the notable role of faculty members in shaping the future of their societies and developing the goals of higher education institutions, as well as the prevalent belief that faculty members who are satisfied with their work and perform their duties more effectively compared with their dissatisfied colleagues (Judge, & et.al, 2001).

Calhoun (1982) asserted that job satisfaction is the degree to which an individual fulfills major demands such as health, security, love, and appreciation during the job. Where Y and Shani (1991) showed that job satisfaction is a set of emotional attitudes by individuals towards jobs, depending on the harmony between the rewards that the work environment provides to the individual and the individual's priorities for these jobs. Job satisfaction is the set of positive or negative feelings that workers in their organizations express regarding leadership, nature of job, salary, incentives, and opportunities for promotion. Job satisfaction constitutes a group of psychological, environmental, and functional factors, which, if available, the worker feels satisfied with the work (Al-Hamami, 1993). Job satisfaction is a positive emotional state arising from an individual's work or practical experiences (Harem, 2004). It was defined according to Schermehon (2000) as the degree of positive or negative feeling of the members of the organization about their work and duties in the organization. It is the degree to which positive or negative feelings are delegated to the work and its aspects (Al-Sayrafi, 2003).

Falih and Abdul Majeed (2005) indicated that job satisfaction has basic elements which are remuneration, job content, nature of work activities, opportunities for achievement, options for success and creativity in the organization, the degree of empowerment, and participation in decision-making. Job satisfaction is a concept that includes special aspects. The most important of which is the nature of the job, colleagues, supervision, salary, promotions system, communication system, and organizational policies (Mansour, 2010).

A set of factors influencing job satisfaction, particularly, the work, job environment, security and stability, incentive system and determination of work goals in addition to relationships with colleagues, work democracy, opportunities for growth and promotion, equal opportunities, and the status of the social position (Al-Ruwaili, 2009).

Obviously, job satisfaction is one of the institutional variables that must be taken into consideration, especially faculty members' relationships with their colleagues, work environment, organizational climate, direct administration, salaries, incentives, and opportunities for professional development. Universities are among the most influential organizations in which officials have to give more attention to the development of faculty members in light of the changes that the world is witnessing in technology, communication, and economics to ensure that they acquire the best methods and a high performance, which guarantees sound qualified outcomes capable of contributing to development and construction programs. Where faculty members are an important focus in university education, which requires paying attention to their job satisfaction, morale, organizational justice, organizational confidence, and other variables related to guarantee the development of their performance levels, which is fully reflected in university performance.

Several previous studies have addressed the degree of job satisfaction of faculty members in universities. For example (Tahainah, Momani, & Tahinah, 2020). conducted a study aimed at identifying the leadership behavior of deans of the Faculties of Physical Education in Jordanian universities and its relationship to the job satisfaction of faculty members and organizational commitment. The sample of the study consisted of (72) faculty members who were chosen randomly from the Faculties of Physical Education in the Jordanian universities) Yarmouk, Mutah ,and Hashemite .(The results revealed that the deans of the Faculties of Physical Education practice leadership behaviors were high according to the faculty members' viewpoint and that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members was high too, as well as in organizational commitment and all areas.

In, 2020 a study was conducted to identify the role of fiscal factors in achieving job satisfaction for Sudanese university professors by (Saleh, Al-Bashir& Al-Jack, 2020)The descriptive-analytical approach was followed, the sample consisted of (370) faculty members from the universities of Al-Jazirah and Khartoum. The findings showed that the faculty members were not satisfied with the compensation system because it did not meet the financial and moral needs of the professors. The incentives also were not commensurate with the efforts of the professors, the university did not provide accommodations and the work environment was poor and not equipped with the means that meet the requirements of the educational process. The offices were also not equipped with furniture and stationery, and professors were not able to enjoy privacy in their offices.

In Poland, a study was conducted to assess the level of job satisfaction among faculty members in higher education institutions by (Szromek, & Wolniak, 2020). and to identify the factors affecting its level. The questionnaire was applied to (712) faculty members. The results of the study showed that faculty members are proud of their work and that their level of satisfaction with social relations at work was high, and work conditions were moderate, while the level of satisfaction with salaries was low. Hee, et, al (2020) conducted a study in Malaysia to study job satisfaction among faculty members in some private universities, and a questionnaire was applied to (82) faculty members. The results showed a relationship between job satisfaction and work environment, pay, and leadership. A study aimed at revealing the relationship between job satisfaction of faculty members and the organizational policy in public and private universities by Durnali, & Ayyildiza(2019) in the city of Ankara in 2020. Two questionnaires were applied to (240) faculty members working in (7) public universities, and (7) private universities. The results of the study showed that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members was very high and that the level of organizational policies came to a high degree, and there was also a relationship between the level of job satisfaction and the level of organizational policies.

Al-Abdan (2019) conducted a study to identify the degree of job satisfaction among faculty members of the Technical College in the cities of Riyadh and Hail and its relationship to their scientific productivity. A questionnaire was applied to (58) faculty members. The results of the study indicated that the degree of job satisfaction among faculty members was highly rated in the fields of job conditions and environment, human relations, salaries, and incentives, and there were no differences according to the variables of nationality and academic rank.

Abu Khudair (2018) conducted a study aimed at identifying the level of job satisfaction among faculty members in public and private Jordanian universities in the northern governorates and to reveal differences in their responses according to the different levels of study variables. The study sample was selected by a stratified method and it consisted of (567) members. The job satisfaction scale prepared by the researcher was applied after checking the reliability and validity, the scale consisted of (45) items distributed into six dimensions. The results of the study showed that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members was moderate and that there were statistically significant differences due to the variable of academic rank, in favor of the rank of professor attributed to the gender variable and in favor of male faculty compared to female faculty.

A study conducted in 2017 aimed to reveal the level of job satisfaction among faculty members in emerging Saudi universities and their relationship to their job stability by Al-Zeaber (2017). The scale of job satisfaction and job stability was applied to a sample consisting of (240) faculty members. The faculty members had a moderate level of satisfaction, and it was found that there were no differences in their responses due to the variables: gender, academic rank, and the number of years of experience, while the differences were found attributed to the nationality variable in favor of the Saudis.

In a study conducted by Al-Dais (2016). aimed at identifying the levels of job satisfaction among faculty members at the University of Sana'a from their viewpoint and defining the role of the variables of specialization and academic rank on their job satisfaction. To achieve the goals of the study, a questionnaire consisted of (45) items was built. It includes these areas: The nature of work, working conditions, promotions and incentives, relationship with officials, salary systems, and relationships with colleagues. The study was applied to (400) faculty members. The study showed that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members was low, and there were statistically significant differences attributable to the academic rank variable, where the differences came in favor of higher ranks.

Duong (2016) conducted a study aimed at identifying job satisfaction among faculty members in Vietnam. The study was applied to (200) faculty members in five colleges at Vietnam National University, and the results showed that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members was moderate. In Sri Lanka, [24] conducted a study aimed to reveal the impact of demographic variables on the degree of job satisfaction of faculty members in Sri Lankan public universities. The sample consisted of (423) faculty members from (15) Sri Lankan public universities, who were randomly selected. To achieve the object of the study, a questionnaire was applied consisting of (30) general questions within demographic variables. Such as current employment status, age, gender, teaching experience, higher educational qualification, and salaries. The results of the study showed that the overall score for job satisfaction was moderate for all faculty members. And there were statistically significant differences in the level of job satisfaction due to the variable of the current situation of work, the monthly salary, and teaching experience in favor of the rank of professor versus the rest of the scientific ranks and in favor of the highest-paid and the most experienced teaching. It was shown that males were more satisfied than females, while no differences were found in the degree of job satisfaction due to the variables of gender and educational level.

In his study Amarasena., Ajward, & Haque (2015) assessed the degree of job satisfaction of faculty members in Jordanian universities. The study sample consisted of (118) faculty members who responded to (75) items. The findings indicated that the faculty members had a moderate level of job satisfaction, and there were differences in the level of job satisfaction according to the gender variable in favor of males, by the experience variable in favor of those with higher experience, and by the university type in favor of public universities. Where in a study conducted by [25] which aimed at identifying the level of job satisfaction of faculty members at Philadelphia University in Jordan, the researcher applied a questionnaire to (199) faculty members, and the results of the study revealed that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members was significantly higher and that there were no differences in the responses of the study sample attributable to the variables: gender, academic rank, and the years of experience.

Mansour (2010) conducted a study aimed at identifying the degree of job satisfaction among faculty members at An-Najah National University, and to determining the effect of the two variables of academic qualification and experience on that. A questionnaire was applied to a sample of (138) faculty members. The results showed that the overall degree of satisfaction was average and that the field of promotions was the lowest. The results also showed statistically significant differences in the degree of satisfaction according to the variables of experience in favor of higher experience, and academic qualification in favor of the lower qualification.

After reviewing the previous studies, we conclude that:

- Most of the previous studies tried to identify the level of job satisfaction of faculty members in universities, and their different responses to some variables.
- Most of the previous studies used the descriptive method for its relevance to such studies.
- Some previous studies sought to link job satisfaction with some variables, organizational loyalty, and organizational scientific productivity.
- Most of the previous studies indicated that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members is moderate.
- The current study is consistent with previous studies in terms of studying the job satisfaction of faculty members, and it is consistent with the tool used, which is the questionnaire.
- The current study differs from previous studies in that it dealt with private and government universities, and in the place of study.
- The researcher benefited from previous studies in building the study tool and discussing its results.

Study Problem

Faculty members are the most influential factor; Given that teaching, scientific research, community service, and other tasks depend mainly on them, therefore, universities administration should provide them with a university healthy environment that motivated them and to met their demands especially job satisfaction in a way that reflects their level of performance and university excellence. Considering the rapid changes that the world is witnessing in all aspects of life, universities are expected to keep pace with this rapid development and provide all the requirements for raising the performance of their faculty members. Job satisfaction is one of the critical variables that should be given attention to, as there are relationships between the level of performance and the level of job satisfaction. Previous studies have indicated different levels of job satisfaction among faculty members that ranged between moderate and high levels. The researcher believes that identifying the level of job satisfaction at King Faisal University in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is a research necessity in light of the changes that the Kingdom is witnessing in all fields, and in light of the various developments that the university is beholding.

Study questions:

The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of job satisfaction among the faculty members at King Faisal University in Saudi Arabia from their viewpoint?
2. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha > 0.05$) between the average responses of the study sample individuals regarding the level of job satisfaction among the faculty members attributable to variables: gender, College, nationality, academic rank, and experience?

Study Objectives:

The study aimed to achieve the following objectives:

1. Identifying the level of job satisfaction among faculty members at King Faisal University.
2. Revealing the differences between the responses of faculty members regarding their level of job satisfaction at different levels of study variables: gender, College, nationality, college, academic rank, and experience.

Study Importance:

The importance of the current study lies in:

- The importance of the work environment and the organizational climate prevailing in universities and the implications for the level of achievement of faculty members.
- The value of a faculty member at the university, as he is responsible for teaching and performing the scientific research that serves his job and the community in which he lives, needs work to ensure all the things that make him feel his position, raise his level of satisfaction with work and increase his productivity.
- The results of the study can reveal the level of job satisfaction of faculty members.
- The information about the differences between the responses of faculty members regarding their job satisfaction level according to different variables that may benefit scholars and researchers in this area.

Study terms:

- **Job satisfaction:** a collection of emotions, attitudes demonstrated by administrative staff and faculty towards the working environment, relationships with colleagues, job security, wages and rewards, and direct administration [26]. Procedurally, it is defined as the overall score obtained by the faculty members after responding to the scale of the study tool prepared by the researcher.
- **King Faisal University:** one of the public universities in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, located in the Al-Ahsa region. It was founded in 1975 and offers undergraduate and postgraduate programs in various fields of education, law, the arts, administrative sciences, research, medicine, and engineering.
- **Faculty member:** someone who holds a doctorate in one of the university's specializations, with academic ranks: professor, associate professor, assistant professor.

Study limits:

- Human Limits: Sample responses from faculty members.
- Spatial boundaries: the scientific and humanitarian colleges of King Faisal University.
- Time limits: The study was conducted at the beginning of the first semester of the 2019/2020 cademic year.
- Objective limits: the level of job satisfaction of faculty members.

Method and procedures

Study Approach

The descriptive approach was adopted by building a questionnaire and applying it to a sample of faculty members at King Faisal University. This approach considered appropriate to achieve the goals of the study and it is a suitable method for measuring the responses of the study sample, it also enables the researcher to provide a comprehensive description and accurate diagnosis of the reality of the phenomenon [28].

Study population:

The study population consisted of all faculty members at King Faisal University in the (15) colleges (scientific colleges and humanities). The faculty members were (2,144) included (1249) males and (895) females, according to the statistics of the Human Resources Department at King Faisal University, at the beginning of the first semester of the 2019/2020 academic year.

The study sample:

The study was applied to a sample of (327) faculty members in the scientific and human colleges at King Faisal University, who were chosen randomly, based on [29], where (252) faculty members responded from different colleges, academic ranks, years of experience, nationality as shown in Table.

Table (1): Distribution of study sample members (faculty members) according to its variables

Variables	Level/category	NO.	Percentage
College	Scientific	85	33.7
	Humanities	167	66.3
	Total	252	100.0
Academic rank	Professor	32	12.7
	Co-professor	73	29.0
	Assistant Professor	147	58.3
	Total	252	100.0
Gender	Male	164	65.1
	female	88	34.9
	Total	252	100.0
Nationality	Saudi	103	40.9
	Non-Saudi	149	59.1
	Total	252	100.0
Years of experience	Less than 5 years	44	17.5
	5 - 10 years	83	32.9
	10 - 15 years old	54	21.4
	15 years and over	71	28.2
	Total	252	100.0

Study tool:

After reviewing the previous literature and studies that address job satisfaction among faculty members, a questionnaire was built consisting (41) items in its initial and distributed into five areas: job, social relations at work, salaries and incentives, direct administration, professional development, and promotions. The respondent ticks the suitable item of the areas on a five-point scale (very high, high, moderate, low, very low). The tool was corrected by giving the following weights (5, 4, 3, 2, 1) for the degrees previously mentioned.

Face validity of the study tool:

The tool was presented in its initial form to (10) arbitrators from the faculty members at King Faisal University in the College of Education, and the Arab Open University in Al-Ahsa, where they were asked to review the tool items and to check their appropriateness, to delete and suggest appropriate items. After considering the arbitrators' suggestions the final form included (36) items distributed on (5) areas.

Construct validity of the study tool (job satisfaction):

The validity of the construction of the study tool regarding job satisfaction was checked by calculating the (Corrected item-total Correlation coefficient) for its items as illustrated in Table (2).

Table (2): Corrected Correlation Coefficient for the items of the study tool: (An exploratory sample of 25 faculty members)

NO.	Correlated coefficient		NO.	Correlated coefficient	
	Related area	Overall tool		Related area	Overall tool
1	0.55	0.60	19	0.68	0.50
2	0.50	0.59	20	0.65	0.49

NO.	Correlated coefficient		NO.	Correlated coefficient	
	Related area	Overall tool		Related area	Overall tool
3	0.56	0.58	21	0.76	0.54
4	0.33	0.26	22	0.68	0.45
5	0.65	0.68	23	0.74	0.64
6	0.52	0.63	24	0.77	0.68
7	0.58	0.69	25	0.73	0.51
8	0.20	0.24	26	0.75	0.60
9	0.72	0.57	27	0.76	0.60
10	0.66	0.34	28	0.65	0.59
11	0.73	0.42	29	0.72	0.60
12	0.72	0.38	30	0.80	0.70
13	0.70	0.39	31	0.74	0.65
14	0.43	0.31	32	0.77	0.68
15	0.62	0.52	33	0.71	0.73
16	0.67	0.55	34	0.67	0.69
17	0.68	0.53	35	0.65	0.57
18	0.69	0.63	36	0.61	0.58

Table (2) illustrates that all values of the corrected correlation coefficient ranged between (0.20 - 0.80), which are acceptable for the goals of the current study.

Table (3): Coefficients for the reliability of internal consistency (Cronbach Alpha) and the Pearson correlation coefficient for the study overall tool and each of its areas.

NO	Areas	Cronbach Alpha	Pearson correlation coefficient
1	Job	0.74	0.79
2	Social relationships at work	0.86	0.81
3	Salaries and incentives	0.89	0.87
4	Direct administration	0.90	0.92
5	Professional development and promotions	0.91	0.90
	The study tool (job satisfaction) as a whole	0.92	0.88

Table (3) shows that the value of the internal consistency coefficient ranged between (0.74) and (0.91) and for the overall tool (0.92). Where the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient ranged between (0.79) and (0.92), which is considered acceptable for the goals of the current study.

The statistical criterion for the study tool (job satisfaction):

To determine the level of job satisfaction among faculty members at King Faisal University and for each of its areas the statistical criterion based on the means was utilized as shown in Table (4).

Table (4): the statistical criterion of job satisfaction based on means.

Mean	Level
1.00-1.80	Very low
1.80-2.60	Low
2.60-3.40	Moderate
3.40-4.20	high
4.20-5.00	Very high

Study variables:

The study included the following variables:

1. **First:** the independent variables:

faculty members including:

- Gender: It has two groups (male and female).
- Academic rank: It has two levels: (Bachelor, Postgraduate).
- Faculty: Scientific, humanitarian.
- Nationality: Saudi, non-Saudi.
- Experience: less than 5 years, 5 - 10 years, 10 - 15 years, 15 years, and above.

2. **Second:** The dependent variables:

- The overall level of job satisfaction of faculty members at King Faisal University is represented by the means of the respondents' estimates on the items of job satisfaction.
- Areas of job satisfaction among faculty members: It is represented by the means of the respondents' estimates on the items of each tool area (job, social relations at work, salaries and incentives, direct administration, professional development, and promotions).

Results

Results regarding the first question:

"What is the level of job satisfaction among faculty members at King Faisal University from their viewpoint?" To answer this question; the overall means and standard deviations of the respondents' estimates were calculated on the items of the study tool " job satisfaction" and on each of its areas (job, social relations at work, salaries and incentives, direct administration, professional development, and promotions) as shown in Table (5).

Table (5): The overall means and standard deviations of the respondents' estimates on the items and each of its areas arranged in descending order

N O	Areas	*Mean	SD	Rank	Level
2	Social relationships at work	4.25	0.61	1	Very high
4	Direct administration	3.95	0.79	2	High
5	Professional development and promotions	3.56	0.64	3	high
1	Job	3.53	0.90	4	high
3	Salaries and incentives	2.76	0.89	5	moderate
	Overall job satisfaction	3.53	0.90		high

* Lowest degree (1) and the highest degree (5).

By studying Table (5) we recognize that the overall level of job satisfaction of the faculty members is (high) with a mean =3.53 and a standard deviation =0.90. Where the second area (social relations at work) ranked first with a mean =4.25 and a (very high) degree, followed by the fourth area (direct administration) with a mean =3.95 and a (high) level, and the fifth area (professional development and promotions) ranked third with a mean =3.56 and with a (high) degree. The first area (job) came fourth with a mean = 3.53 and a (high) degree, while the third area (salaries and incentives) ranked last with a Mean = 2.76 and a (moderate) level.

Table (5) also shows that one area came at a very high level, which is (social relations at work), and three areas come at a high level, which are (direct administration, professional development, and promotions, job) respectively, and one area came at a medium level, which is (salaries and incentives).

The researcher attributes these findings to several reasons when the faculty members achieve work security, it will reflect thoroughly on increasing the level of job satisfaction and raising the morale and working hard and diligently, and dealing with friendliness, appreciation. Actually, respect in the work environment encourages faculty members on promoting institutional achievement and loyalty. Practicing justice and the democratic leadership style encourages faculty members to participate in decision-making, providing consultations, and raising their level of job satisfaction. Logically, the teaching profession as a faculty member at the university, makes them proud of this job because society appreciates this category and considers them the important link in the development of society. While the researcher attributes the moderate results regarding salary to the rapid changes that included all countries of the world, and the global economic crisis that affected countries; It sought to impose some taxes to avoid the effects of the economic crises, especially in light of the global decline in oil prices. Consequently, salaries are not at the level that achieves the welfare of faculty members, or the standard of living they aspire to, because families have many commitments in terms of

educating children in some private schools or repaying loans for buying a house or a car. The result of all areas except the result regarding salaries is consistent with the results of the study of Tahainah, Momani, & Tahinah (2020). which showed that the overall level of job satisfaction among faculty members was high. And with the results of the Durnali, & Ayyildiza (2019) which showed that the level of job satisfaction of faculty members was very high. It was also consistent with the results of Szromek, & Wolniak(2020)which showed that faculty members are proud of their work and that their level of satisfaction with social relations at work was high, and with the results of (Al-Abdan, 2019) study, which showed that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members was high on the areas of working conditions and environment, and human relations. It was also consistent with the results of (Jalabna, 2011)which showed that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members was significantly higher. On the other hand, it differs from the results of (Jalabna, 2011)in which the results of working conditions were moderate, while the level of satisfaction with salaries was low. Where it is inconsistent with the results of (Abu Khdeir, 2018)which indicated that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members in Jordanian universities in the northern governorates was of a moderate degree, and it differs with the results (Al-Zeaber, 2017),(Duong, 2016), (Amarasena., Ajward, & Haque, 2015)and (Al-Ruwaili, 2009) which showed that the level of job satisfaction among faculty members came with a moderate level, and with the results of (Al-Dais, 2016), which revealed a low level of job satisfaction among faculty members.

Means and standard deviations of the respondents' estimates were gauged on each item of each of the study tool areas considering job satisfaction (job, social relations at work, salaries and incentives, direct administration, professional development, and promotions) as indicated in Table (6).

Table (6): Mean and standard deviations of the respondents' estimates on the scale area

NO.	Item	Mean*	SD	Rank	Level
The first area: The job :					
8	I have a stable job at my university.	3.81	3.92	1	high
2	The university clearly states job responsibilities.	3.67	0.94	2	high
1	The university appreciates the work I do.	3.61	0.98	3	high
6	The university gives me independence and self-control at work.	3.58	1.02	4	high
4	I think the halls, laboratories and the equipment provided are adequate.	3.41	1.23	5	high
3	I feel satisfied with the study plans and programs.	3.40	0.90	6	high
7	Opportunities exist to put my views and ideas into action.	3.40	0.99	7	high
5	The university provides me with appropriate opportunities for innovation and creativity at work.	3.36	1.05	8	moderate
	Total	3.53	0.90		high
The second area: social relations at work:					
10	My colleagues and I respect and appreciate each other.	4.58	0.65	1	Very high
11	Tolerance and friendliness prevail between my colleagues and me	4.54	0.66	2	Very high
12	I enjoy understanding and harmony between myself and my colleagues.	4.49	0.68	3	Very high
13	Colleagues deal with honesty and kindness with me and with each other.	4.37	0.74	4	Very high
9	Cooperation prevails between my colleagues and me in the completion of work.	4.22	0.85	5	Very high
15	I collaborate with co-workers to solve problems within the department	4.12	0.93	6	high
14	My colleagues and I made sure to exchange visits at social events.	3.46	1.16	7	high
	Total	4.25	0.61		Very high
The third field: salaries and incentives:					
20	The wage appropriately covers the cost of living.	3.19	1.00	1	moderate
16	The amount of salary I get from college is equivalent to my effort.	3.00	1.06	2	moderate
19	My pay is consistent relative to those of other colleagues.	2.94	1.28	3	moderate
21	My wage provides me the luxury I need.	2.90	1.09	4	moderate
18	There are fairness and transparency in the distribution of additional rewards.	2.74	1.21	5	moderate
17	I receive financial rewards other than salary.	2.30	1.16	6	low
22	The university offers some bonuses and extra salaries.	2.25	1.19	7	low
	Total	2.76	0.89		moderate
The fourth area: salaries and bonuses::					
25	My administrators deal with my colleagues and me without bias when distributing the teaching load.	4.10	0.96	1	high
27	My bosses understand the individual circumstances of me and colleagues with an appreciation for our feelings.	4.01	0.91	2	high
23	My bosses are distinguished by their ability to guide and follow up.	3.99	0.93	3	high
24	My superiors deal with my colleagues and me fairly and equally.	3.91	0.93	4	high

26	I get recognition from my superiors when I perform at work	3.91	0.97	5	high
28	My bosses use my ideas and suggestions when making decisions.	3.78	1.05	6	high
	Total	3.95	0.79		high
	The fifth area: Direct Administration:				
33	The university encourages me to develop my abilities by providing me with new skills.	3.69	1.10	1	high
34	My bosses guide me in avoiding weaknesses for improvement and development.	3.64	1.07	2	high
32	The university guarantees the principle of equal opportunities for promotion.	3.52	1.14	3	high
30	The university encourages me to scientific production for promotion.	3.44	1.20	4	high
31	The university is keen to link promotion with competence and mastery of work.	3.35	1.16	5	moderate
36	The university allows me to be a member of local and international higher bodies in the field of specialization.	3.28	1.28	6	moderate
29	University offers me opportunities to be promoted to a higher rank at work.	3.23	1.24	7	moderate
35	The university gives me opportunities to participate in local and foreign conferences.	3.10	1.28	8	moderate
	Total	3.41	0.93		high
	The overall tool (job satisfaction)	3.56	0.64		high

*lowest degree (1) and highest degree (5)

Table (6) shows the means and standard deviations for the item of each area of job satisfaction. job area which includes (8) items came with the highest mean= 3.81 and a high degree, while item(5) ranked last with a mean= 3.36 and a moderate. Social relations at work which has (10) items record the highest mean= 4.58 and with a very high degree, while item (14) got the lowest mean= 3.46 and with a high degree. In the area regarding salaries and incentives, item (20) obtained a mean = 3.19 with a moderate level, while item (22) ranked last with a mean=2.25 and a low degree. Also, Item (25) of the direct administration area obtained the highest mean = 4.10 with a high degree, and that all items in this area reached a high degree. Where in the professional development and promotions area item (33) recorded the highest mean= 3.69 with a high degree, and that item (35) got the lowest mean= 3.10 with a moderate degree.

The results of the second question, which stated:

“Are there statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha > 0.05$) between the average responses of the study sample individuals regarding the level of job satisfaction among the faculty members attributable to variables: gender, nationality, academic rank, and experience?”

To answer this question; The overall means and standard deviations of the respondents' estimates were gauged on the items of the study tool regarding job satisfaction that attributable to the variables (college, academic rank, gender, nationality, number of years of experience) as shown in Table(7).

Table (7): The overall mean and SD of the respondents' estimates on the items of the scale according to the variables

Variable	Level/category	Mean	SD
College	Scientific	3.55	0.67
	humanities	3.57	0.62
	Total	3.56	0.64
Academic rank	professor	3.38	0.63
	Co-professor	3.73	0.55
	Assistant Professor	3.52	0.66
	Total	3.56	0.64
Gender	Male	3.71	0.57

Variable	Level/category	Mean	SD
	female	3.30	0.67
	Total	3.56	0.64
Nationality	Saudi	3.47	0.66
	Non-Saudi	3.63	0.61
	Total	3.56	0.64
Years of Experience	Less than 5 years	3.55	0.63
	5 - 10 years	3.60	0.68
	10 - 15 years old	3.58	0.61
	15 years and over	3.51	0.61
	Total	3.56	0.64

Table (7) shows that there are significant differences between the overall mean of the respondents' estimates on the items of the study tool concerning job satisfaction attributable to the variables (college, academic rank, gender, nationality, and the number of years of experience), and to determine the statistical significance for these significant differences, Five-way ANOVA was applied as indicated in Table (8).

Table (8): ANOVA of the overall means of the respondents' estimates on the scale

Variable	SS	DF	MS	F value	Sig
the college	0.200	1	0.200	0.549	0.459
Academic rank	2.007	2	1.003	2.755	0.066
Gender	7.440	1	7.440	*20.434	0.000
Nationality	0.441	1	0.441	1.212	0.272
Years of Experience	0.755	3	0.252	0.691	0.558
The error	88.481	243	0.364		
Adjusted Total	101.264	251			

* Statistically significant at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$)

Table (8) shows that:

- The value of the statistical significance of the total variable =0.459, which is greater than the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). This indicates that there is no statistically significant difference at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the two arithmetic averages of the estimates of the study sample members (faculty members) on the items of the study tool related to job satisfaction as a whole due to the college variable.
- The value of the statistical significance of the variable of academic rank was (0.066), which is greater than the level of statistical significance ($0.05 = \alpha$). This indicates that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the overall means of the respondents' estimates on the items of the study tool regarding job satisfaction attributed to the variable of academic rank. This means that faculty members of different academic ranks agree on the level of job satisfaction that it is at a high degree except for the area of salaries, and this indicates the actual reality of the level of job satisfaction at King Faisal University. This result is consistent with the results of (Al-Abdan, 2019), (Al-Zeaber, 2017) and (Jalabna, 2011) which showed no differences attributed to the variable of academic rank. While it differs from the results of (Al-Dais, 2016), which showed that there are statistically significant differences according to the variable of academic rank, where the differences came in favor of higher ranks.
- The value of the statistical significance of the gender variable reached (0.000), which is less than the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). This indicates that there is a statistically significant difference at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the overall of the two means of the respondents' estimates on the items of the study tool related to job satisfaction attributed to the gender variable. By examining the table of means we notice that the statistically significant difference is in favor of Males. This result is consistent with the results of (Abu Khdeir, 2018) and (Bataneh, 2014) which indicated that there are statistically significant differences attributed to the gender variable that is in favor of male faculty members compared to females. This result may be attributed to the fact that male faculty members focus on all aspects of overall job satisfaction, while females pay more attention to details than males, and therefore their assessment is lower than males. However, the results differ

from the results of the (Al-Zeaber, 2017), (Al-Dais, 2016), and (Jalabna, 2011), which showed no differences in the participants' responses due to the gender variable.

- The value of the statistical significance of the variable of nationality was (0.272), which is greater than the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). This indicates that there is no statistically significant difference at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the overall of the two means of the participants' estimates on the items of the study tool regarding job satisfaction due to the nationality variable. This result may be attributed to the fact that Saudi faculty members and contractor from the faculty members from other countries are subject to the same university laws, direct administration is the same, and they are treated in the same way. This result is consistent with the results of (Al-Abdan, 2019) which showed no differences attributable to the nationality variable. However, it differs from the results (Al-Zeaber, 2017) which showed that there are differences due to the nationality variable and in favor of Saudis.
- The value of the statistical significance of the variable of years of experience is (0.558), which is greater than the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). This indicates that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the overall means of the participants' estimates on the items of the study tool regarding job satisfaction attributable to the variable of years of experience. This result is attributed to the fact that the reality the salaries and incentives at colleges of King Faisal University, work environment, social relations are known to every faculty member regardless of their years of experience. The results of this study differ from the results of (Amarasena., Ajward, & Haque, 2015(Bataineh, 2014), and (Al-Ruwaili, 2009) which showed statistically significant differences in the level of job satisfaction attributable to the variable of teaching experiences which is in favor of the most experienced faculty members.

The means and standard deviations of the respondents' estimates were calculated for each field of the study tool regarding job satisfaction (job itself, social relationships at work, salaries and incentives, direct administration, professional growth, and promotions) due to the variable (college, rank Academic, gender, nationality, number of years of experience) as shown in Table (9).

Table (9): The means and standard deviations of the respondents' estimates on each area of the study tool according to the variable (college, academic rank, gender, nationality, number of years of experience, specialization)

Variables	Level/category	Job		Relationship at work		Salaries &incentives		Direct administration		Professional development & promotion	
		mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD
College	Scientific	3.54	1.12	4.23	0.63	2.79	0.87	3.90	0.82	3.37	0.96
	humanities	3.53	0.76	4.26	0.60	2.75	0.90	3.98	0.77	3.42	0.91
	Total	3.53	0.90	4.25	0.61	2.76	0.89	3.95	0.79	3.41	0.93
Academic rank	professor	3.26	0.77	4.13	0.72	2.67	0.84	3.81	0.77	3.14	0.94
	Co-professor	3.62	0.70	4.35	0.51	3.02	0.94	4.09	0.68	3.65	0.79
	Assistant Professor	3.54	0.99	4.23	0.62	2.65	0.85	3.91	0.83	3.34	0.96
	Total	3.53	0.90	4.25	0.61	2.76	0.89	3.95	0.79	3.41	0.93
Gender	Male	3.69	0.91	4.30	0.55	3.02	0.83	4.01	0.73	3.58	0.85
	Female	3.24	0.80	4.16	0.69	2.29	0.80	3.83	0.87	3.09	0.98
	Total	3.53	0.90	4.25	0.61	2.76	0.89	3.95	0.79	3.41	0.93
Nationality	Saudi	3.27	0.76	4.22	0.61	2.76	0.92	3.83	0.87	3.36	0.99
	Non-Saudi	3.71	0.94	4.28	0.60	2.76	0.87	4.03	0.72	3.44	0.88
	Total	3.53	0.90	4.25	0.61	2.76	0.89	3.95	0.79	3.41	0.93
Years of experience	Less than 5 years	3.55	0.72	4.21	0.62	2.62	0.81	3.91	0.82	3.54	0.93
	5 - 10 years	3.69	1.13	4.27	0.68	2.77	0.88	3.99	0.79	3.37	0.95
	10 - 15 years	3.44	0.76	4.25	0.53	2.81	0.99	4.05	0.76	3.46	0.83

Variables	Level/category	Job		Relationship at work		Salaries & incentives		Direct administration		Professional development & promotion	
		mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD
	old										
	15 years and over	3.40	0.75	4.27	0.57	2.80	0.89	3.85	0.79	3.33	0.97
	Total	3.53	0.90	4.25	0.61	2.76	0.89	3.95	0.79	3.41	0.93

Table (9) illustrates that there are significant differences between the means of the estimates of the participants in each field of the study tool regarding job satisfaction (job, social relations at work, salaries and bonuses, direct management, professional growth, and promotions), According to the variables (college, academic rank, gender, nationality, and the number of years of experience), and to determine the statistical significance of these significant differences, Five-way MANOVA analysis was applied as shown in Table (10).

Table (10): Five-way MANOVA analysis of the means of respondents estimates according to a variable (college, academic rank, gender, nationality, number of years of experience)

Source of variance	Area	SS	DF	MS	F value	Sig
College Hoteling's Trace=0.005 Sig=0.934	Job	0.016	1	0.016	0.022	0.882
	Social relationships at work	0.060	1	0.060	0.161	0.688
	Salaries and incentive	0.255	1	0.255	0.380	0.538
	Direct administration	0.492	1	0.492	0.808	0.370
	Professional development and promotions	0.497	1	0.497	0.628	0.429
Academic rank Wilks' Lambda=0.945 Sig=0.188	Job	1.438	2	0.719	0.996	0.371
	Social relationships at work	0.791	2	0.395	1.065	0.346
	Salaries and incentive	3.691	2	1.845	2.751	0.066
	Direct administration	1.367	2	0.683	1.124	0.327
	Professional development and promotions	5.800	2	2.900	2.864	0.062
Gender Hoteling's Trace=0.161 Sig= *0.000	Job	6.665	1	6.665	*9.236	0.003
	Social relationships at work	0.849	1	0.849	2.287	0.132
	Salaries and incentive	28.943	1	28.943	*43.152	0.000
	Direct administration	0.953	1	0.953	1.566	0.212
	Professional development and promotions	11.883	1	11.883	15.013 *	0.000
Nationality Hoteling's Trace=0.132 Sig= *0.000	Job	8.844	1	8.844	*12.256	0.001
	Social relationships at work	0.029	1	0.029	0.077	0.781
	Salaries and incentive	1.641	1	1.641	2.447	0.119
	Direct administration	1.955	1	1.955	3.214	0.074
	Professional development and promotions	0.004	1	0.004	0.005	0.946
Years of experience Wilks' Lambda=0.920 Sig=0.164	Job	4.305	3	1.435	1.989	0.116
	Social relationships at work	0.081	3	0.027	0.072	0.975

Source of variance	Area	SS	DF	MS	F value	Sig
	Salaries and incentive	0.102	3	0.034	0.051	0.985
	Direct administration	1.532	3	0.511	0.840	0.473
	Professional development and promotions	3.433	3	1.144	1.446	0.230
Error	Job	175.356	243	0.722		
	Social relationships at work	90.262	243	0.371		
	Salaries and incentive	162.984	243	0.671		
	Direct administration	147.807	243	0.608		
	Professional development and promotions	192.335	243	0.792		
Adjusted total	Job	201.129	251			
	Social relationships at work	92.544	251			
	Salaries and incentive	199.102	251			
	Direct administration	155.152	251			
	Professional development and promotions	214.809	251			

*Statistically significant at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$).

When reviewing Table (10) we recognize that:

- The value of the statistical significance of (Hotelling's) according to the college variable = 0.934, which is greater than the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). This indicates that there is no statistically significant difference at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the two means of the respondents' estimates on the field (Job, social relations at work, salaries and incentives, direct administration, professional development, and promotions) attributable to a college variable.
- The value of the statistical significance of (Wilks' Lambda) test according to the variable of academic rank = 0.188, which is more than the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$); This indicates that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the means of the participants' estimates in the field (job, social relations at work, salaries and bonuses, direct management, professional growth, and promotions) attributed to the academic rank variable.
- The value of the statistical significance of (Hotelling's) according to the gender variable = 0.000 which is less than the level of statistical significance ($0.05 = \alpha$); This show that there is a statistically significant difference at least in one of the study tool areas regarding job satisfaction (job, social relations at work, salaries and incentives, direct administration, professional development, and promotions). Given the statistical significance of area (10), it was less than the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). Accordingly, this indicates a statistically significant difference at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the two means of the respondents' estimates on the area (job itself, salaries and incentives, professional development and promotions) due to the gender variable, and from the table of the means, we can notice that the significant difference comes in favor of males variable.
- The value of the statistical significance of (Hotelling's) according to a variable = 0.000 this result is to a lesser extent than the level of statistical significance ($0.05 = \alpha$); This indicates a statistically significant difference at least in one of the study tool areas concerning job satisfaction (job, social relations at work, salaries and incentives, direct administration, professional development, and promotions). Considering the statistical significance of the areas (job, salaries, and incentives, professional development, and promotions), the result was less than the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) which reveal the statistically significant difference at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the two averages of the participants estimates on the areas (job, salaries, and incentives, professional development, and promotions) attributed to the gender variable, and by examining the means in the table above we can see that the statistically significant difference is in favor of non-Saudi faculty members.

- The value of the statistical significance of the (Wilks' test) according to the variable of years of experience = 0.164, which is considered greater than the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). This indicates that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the means of the respondents' estimates in the area (job, social relations at work, salaries and incentives, direct administration, professional development, and promotions) attributable to the variable years of experience.

Recommendations:

Considering the results of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

- Inviting officials at King Faisal University to work on improving the salaries of faculty members to be in line with the changes and developments taking place in the world, in a way that provides them with a kind of luxury and fulfilling the requirements of life.
- Inviting officials at King Faisal University to develop a rewarding system that allows the faculty member who is distinguished in teaching, scientific research, and community service to attain financial incentives and rewards.
- Allowing faculty members to participate in local and international conferences without administrative or financial complications.
- Enabling the faculty members at King Faisal University to register for membership in local and international bodies in their field of specialization.

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